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WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Lady constitutes the family, which prompts society and Nation. Social and monetary improvement of ladies is vital for general financial advancement of any general public or a nation. Enterprise is the perspective which each lady has in her however has not been promoted in India in manner by which it ought to be. Because of progress in condition, now individuals are more agreeable to acknowledge driving part of ladies in our general public, however there are a few exemptions.

Our expanding reliance on benefit division has made numerous entrepreneurial open doors particularly for ladies where they can exceed expectations their abilities with keeping up adjust in their life.

Propose of this exact investigation is expected to discover different propelling and de-spurring interior and outside elements of ladies business enterprise. It is an endeavor to measure some for non parametric components to give the feeling of positioning these variables. It will likewise propose the method for dispensing with and lessening obstacles of the ladies business enterprise improvement in Indian Context.

Key words: Enterprise, Entrepreneurship, Women, India

Introduction- The topic of women entrepreneurs has attracted a considerable amount of academic attention in recent years. Indeed, it is fast becoming a primary focus for scholars, practitioners, and policy makers worldwide who work in the field of small business management and entrepreneurship. Generally speaking, women entrepreneurs have been in the minority in comparison to their male counterparts and are still the largest underrepresented group in entrepreneurship. For example, despite the fact that women make up half of the European population, less than one third of all businesses in Europe are female-led. However, it is now widely accepted that women as entrepreneurs make a valuable contribution to national economies around the world in terms of job creation, economic growth, and wealth generation. Contrary to traditional perceptions about women entrepreneurs starting mainly small and home-based enterprises, it has also been reported that women are now leading the so-called “new economy companies,” with success in high technology, life sciences, and professional services. Thus, the need to increase their participation in the enterprise arena is becoming more important to future economic growth.

Research on women’s entrepreneurship has developed significantly in recent years. According to S. Carter and Shaw (2006), the field of women’s entrepreneurship has moved away from purely exploratory

and descriptive studies, characterized by the earlier literature, toward developing stronger evidence bases that report the actual experiences of women's enterprise in international contexts along with a more sophisticated understanding of complex issues (see, e.g., Carter, Henry, Ö Cinnéide, & Johnston, 2006). This research-paper discusses the main themes on women's entrepreneurship, as characterized by the extant literature in this field. It begins with a consideration of the underrepresentation of women in entrepreneurship globally and makes the economic case for encouraging more women to become entrepreneurs. The research-paper then discusses the definitional issues associated with the topic, illustrating how these can restrict the scope for robust comparative studies and impact on research findings. Some trends in women's entrepreneurship internationally are then considered, drawing mainly on the work of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) and the Diana Project.¹ Some of the key characteristics of women entrepreneurs are then discussed, including their motivations for becoming entrepreneurs, their education and work experience, and their levels of confidence and their risk orientation. A major theme in the literature on women's entrepreneurship has been the barriers and challenges they face in their efforts to engage in entrepreneurship. Under this heading, the discussion covers the traditional role of women and their networking practices, access to finance, the tendency to undercapitalize their business, and growth perceptions.

Challenges faced by women entrepreneurs:

1. Tough competition against male counterparts For a long time, entrepreneurship has been a field dominated by men. And while the scenario is changing, there is still a long way to go.

For example, India has the third largest start-up base in the entire world. Over 1,000 new start-ups were added in the last year. Yet the percentage of female start-up founders in India is a measly 11%.

2. Limited funding Funding is crucial in order to start a business. However, a large number of Indian women do not have property or assets to their name. Hence, they encounter a problem while applying for loans due to lack of collateral. This isn't just a problem in India but across the world. A report by Bloomberg showed that women who own and run businesses receive a lot less funding as compared to what men get.

3. Work-life balance Women, across the world, are expected to play a larger part in handling a household and taking care of their family. Owning and running a business means long hours and thus, for women work-life balance can become a problem.

In the case of working mothers, taking care of their children takes up a lot of time and energy, thereby often forcing them to give less priority to their business. Men, on the other hand, generally play a secondary role when it comes to household responsibilities. However, this situation seems to be changing now as more men are stepping forward to contribute to the household responsibilities.

4. Minimal support When you start an entrepreneurial venture and are finding your place in the business world, you need as much support as you can get. Unfortunately, in many cases, women find themselves on their own with no one to guide them. In this day and age, it is almost necessary to have experienced mentors and role models. For women, managing their business becomes even more difficult if their

family and friends don't step up to take some household and family responsibilities. As a result, it can be tough to make a mark in an arena that is already dominated by men.

5. Lack of education Women form 68% of the country's illiterate population, says UNESCO's education report. Female entrepreneurs without formal education can face numerous problems when it comes to issues such as business development, maintaining accounts, understanding money matters or even day-to-day running of the company. Lack of skills, information and the necessary resources to run a business can reduce their chances of turning their business into a success.

Women entrepreneurs in INDIA

India ranked 29th of 31 countries in the 2015 Global Women Entrepreneurs Leader report by ACG Inc, a consultancy, above only Pakistan and Bangladesh. With 17 points of a possible 100, India fared worse than countries such as Nigeria, Uganda and Ghana.

Global Ranks

Measures that need to be taken can to boost Women Entrepreneurship

- Increase skill development and capacity building processes for soft skills, technology and management skills.
- Simplify the external entrepreneurial ecosystem by enabling ease of doing business, including easy access to credit facilities such as collateral-free loans from banks, FIs and MFIs.
- Increase mentoring and market linked to support for women owned enterprises through networks like women entrepreneur associations. Share knowledge resources and document.
- Create awareness of government scheme eligibility criteria, documentation and clearance mechanisms. Bring in smarter technology, single-window clearances and better interdepartmental co-ordination to enable simpler, faster, transparent and effective service delivery for women startups.
- Increase the women's support systems like child care and family support.

REASONS FOR WOMEN OPTING FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Self determination, expectation for recognition, self esteem and career goal are the key drivers for taking up entrepreneurship by women (Moore & Buttner, 1997). Sometimes, women chose such career path for discovering their inner potential, caliber in order to achieve self satisfaction. It can also provide a mean to make best use of their leisure hours. However, dismal economic conditions of the women arising out of unemployment in the family and divorce can compel women into entrepreneurial activities.

OBJECTIVES:

- To identify the reasons for women for involving themselves in entrepreneurial activities
- To identify the factors of hindrance for women entrepreneurship
- To determine the possible success factors for women in such entrepreneurial activities.
- To make an evaluation of people's opinion about women entrepreneurship.

METHODOLOGY

The research is based on secondary & primary data. It's an exploratory & descriptive in nature. The secondary data is collected from review of past researches and other reports. The factors have been identified then classified into three categories factors responsible for hindrance, reasons for starting the business & reasons for success in women entrepreneurship. Then these factors with their sub-classification rated on likert scale of 1 to 5, where 1 denotes least important & 5 denote most important. Then these factors have been further analyzed through Chi square test to check the difference between opinions collected from different sets of people. PSW 18 has been use for calculation purposes.

The data has been collected from the female PGDM students & faculty members only. It is just have common areas of concerns in both the sample group. All the three forms of factors analyzed from the view points of marital status & occupation. Results show that one basis of marital status we find major differences of opinion at significance level of 5. These are need for Money & others factors on which these two sets of people have different opinion. However in hindrance reason we could not find any

significant difference. When it comes on success factors Marketing skills & Preservation also have significant difference. (Refer hypothesis test summary for marital status in annexure)

On the basis of occupation differences are more because two sets have difference in generation also. Students & faculty members have significant differences on various issues almost in every set of factors. Starting from hindrance factors they significantly differ on Raising Capital, Information & advice, skills & expertise, Gender discriminations & others. In the second category of factors i.e. reasons for starting business factors for significant difference are passion; need for money, to become independent, self satisfaction & others. In the category of success factors difference are on the issues like quality of product & service, uniqueness of design & services, management skills & marketing skills & preservation.

CONCLUSION

The investigation endeavored to discover the distinction among different arrangement of individuals of the pivotal elements which are worried about the ladies entrepreneurial open doors on the loose. Issues have been recognized through different survey of writing. It ought to be cross checked with the genuine business people. These elements may change from place to put business to business however ladies enterprise is important for the development of any economy climate it extensive or little.

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